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LAVOISIER INTERNATIONAL CHEMISTRY
OLYMPIAD, HONDURAS TST

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LAVOISIER INTERNATIONAL CHEMISTRY OLYMPIAD, HONDURAS TST

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Abstract

The Lavoisier International Chemistry Olympiad (LiChO) is an online international Chemistry competition. This competition is organized by the Organizing Center for STEM Olympiad (OCSO), a non-profit organization in the field of STEM development around the world. The main objective of the LiChO is fostering a positive attitude, especially in terms of critical thinking and being scientific through the challenges of solving Chemistry problems. In this article, we present the Team Selection Test (TST) used to select the team that represented Honduras in this competition.

Keywords: Honduras, LiChO, critical thinking, chemistry problems, chemistry competition.

Olimpiada Internacional de Química Lavoisier – TST

Resumen

La Olimpiada Internacional de Química Lavoisier (LiChO) es una competencia internacional de química la cual está organizada por el Organizing Center for STEM Olympiad (OCSO), una organización sin ánimo de lucro en el ámbito del desarrollo de STEM en todo el mundo. El objetivo principal de la LiChO es fomentar una actitud positiva, especialmente en lo que se refiere al pensamiento crítico y al ser científico a través de los retos de la resolución de problemas de Química. En este artículo, presentamos la Prueba de Selección de Equipos (TST) utilizada para seleccionar al equipo que representó a Honduras en esta competencia.

Palabras clave: Honduras, LiChO, pensamiento crítico, problemas de química, competencia de química.

Lavoisier International Chemistry Olympiad

Honduras TST

1. A sealed 200.0 mL container at 400.0 K and a pressure of 840.0 Torr contains Gas X, a gaseous compound consisting of only xenon and fluorine, and Xenon Tetroxide.
 - a. Explain why these gases deviate significantly from being an Ideal Gas.
 - b. What is the pressure, in atm, of the container if the temperature is raised to 1000 °C?
 - c. If the partial pressure of Gas X is 0.130 atm at 400.0 K, what is the molar concentration of Xenon Tetroxide in the container?
 - d. Given that the ratio of effusion rates of Gas X to Xenon Tetroxide is 0.8923, find the identity of gas X.
 - e. Which gas has a higher average speed at 400K? Provide your reasoning.

2. Write net ionic equations for the following reactions. You need not balance the reactions.
 - a. A piece of solid calcium carbonate is reacted with dilute nitric acid.
 - b. Dilute sodium hydroxide is mixed with dilute hydrochloric acid.
 - c. Carbon dioxide is bubbled into a solution of calcium hydroxide.
 - d. A piece of solid sodium was thrown into a beaker containing water.
 - e. Solutions of silver nitrate and potassium iodide are mixed.

3. A galvanic cell was constructed using copper, zinc, and their respective 1 M sulfate solutions. The reaction is carried out under 25 °C and 1 atm. The half-reactions are shown below.

- a. Draw a diagram of the galvanic cell with all necessary components and label each component.
- b. Write the equation for the overall reaction and calculate the cell potential.
- c. When setting up the galvanic cell, a student mistakenly used a 0.1 M solution of ZnSO_4 instead of the intended 1 M solution. Calculate the cell potential under this condition.
- d. Predict the qualitative effect on the cell potential if some NaOH is added to the cathodic compartment.

4. Consider this electrophilic addition reaction:

- Calculate the theoretical yield, in grams, of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$ if the reaction is conducted with 2.50 grams of C_2H_4 and 1.20 grams of chlorine.
- The final yield of $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$ was 1.20g. Calculate the percent yield of this reaction.
- Is the product molecule polar? Identify the type(s) of intermolecular forces the product molecule exhibits.
- Are the hydrogen atoms on each carbon in $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$ located on the same plane? Explain.
- Using the table below, determine the order of the reaction with respect to each reactant.

Partial Pressure of Cl_2 (atm)	Partial Pressure of C_2H_4 (atm)	Rate of Reaction (atm per second)
0.3	0.3	0.0071837
0.3	0.6	0.0071837
0.6	0.3	0.0143674
0.6	0.6	0.0143674

5.

Phenol, pictured above, is an organic alcohol with one acidic proton, the one attached to the oxygen atom ($\text{pK}_a = 10.0$). 50. mL of a solution containing phenol is titrated with a standardized solution of 0.20 M NaOH. 67 mL of the NaOH solution was required to completely neutralize all the phenol.

- Write the equation for the reaction of phenol with NaOH.
- Find the original concentration of phenol.
- What is the pH at the endpoint?

6.

$$\Delta G = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad \Delta G^\circ = -RT \ln K_{eq} \quad \ln\left(\frac{p_2}{p_1}\right) = \frac{\Delta H_{\text{vap}}}{R} \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2}\right)$$

a. For the reaction

The change in Gibbs free energy is 8.43 kJ/mol under standard conditions. What is the vapor pressure of water, in mmHg, at 52.0 degrees Celsius?

- b. At the top of Mount Everest, the atmospheric pressure is 0.33 atm. What would the normal boiling point of water be at this point? ΔH_{vap} of water is 40.8 kJ/mol.
- c. Find ΔS_{vap} of water at 52 degrees Celsius.

7. Consider the following reaction scheme. Platinum electrodes are placed in a beaker containing only compound **A** mixed with compound **D**, and a strong current is passed through them. At one electrode, a gas **B** is evolved, and at the other electrode, a gas **C** is evolved. Twice as much **B** is evolved compared to **C**, and gas **B** is commonly used in the reduction of unsaturated organic compounds. Compound **D** is 22.57% sulfur by mass and 32.37% sodium by mass. Identify compounds **A - D**.

8.

$$\frac{1}{\lambda} = R_H \left(\frac{1}{n_f^2} - \frac{1}{n_i^2} \right)$$

- a. Explain why the hydrogen emission spectra consists of discrete lines instead of a continuous spectrum of light.
- b. Explain, using the equation given above, why the hydrogen emission spectra lines become closer together at shorter wavelengths.

In 1922, Albert Einstein won the Nobel Prize for his discovery of the photoelectric effect. The photoelectric effect is the emission of electrons when electromagnetic radiation, such as light, hits a metal.

- c. Explain what would happen to the electrons begin ejected if the intensity of the light being projected onto the metal was increased.

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